

Journey from Shruti to Blending Mode of Education: A Complete Discussion of Learning Environment in India

Dr Uttam Kumar Hazra

Librarian, Vivekananda Mahavidyalaya, Burdwan, P. O. – Sripally, Dist. – PurbaBardhaman, PIN–713103, ORCID:<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9041-6901>, E-mail: uttamlib@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

All human beings need education for their cultural and social development today. But the education system has changed over time, from the Vedic period to the present Information and Communication Technology-dominated era. The present paper, entitled "Journey from Shruti to Blending Mode of Education: A Complete Discussion of Learning Environment in India", focuses on the evolution of the Indian education system from ancient times to the present. This research is based on reliable literature from the fields of literature and anthropology. This research found that the Vedic period marked the beginning of education. After that, the education system has been changed and developed over time, and with the advent of Information and Communication Technology, the E-Learning System, Digital Learning System, Virtual Learning Environment, Managed Learning Environment, MOOC, and Blended Learning have been introduced. But above all, "the basic pattern is almost the same".

Introduction: Learning is the key to acquiring the full potential of human beings. It is the bearer of a nation's culture and civilisation, and to give it its proper shape, learning, so-called education, is always dependable. For the time being, the economic and social life of human beings has changed with the development of education, and economic and social development has compelled a change in the philosophy of life, consciousness of religion, national politics, etc. () The ups and downs of these components of society have created a remarkable history and heritage of national life and have also

shaped the education system. The Education System in the ancient period, the Education System in modern times, and the Education System with the application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) are discussed in the present article.

Objectives:The following are the objectives:

- i. To discuss the education system in the ancient period, modern period, British period and post-independence period;
- ii. To narrate the education system with the advent of ICT;
- iii. To find out the consequences before and after the application of ICT in learning.

Methodology: This is qualitative research. The researcher gathers information on related topics from various sources, such as books, journal articles, theses, and dissertations, both online and offline, and then analyses the outcomes from these sources. Thus, the researcher concludes.

Analysis:

Education System in the Ancient Period:This period began with the appearance of human beings on this planet. Education began in the Vedic period, but it is tough to describe the education system at that time, as the account depends entirely on literary and anthropological sources. Literary components are divided into two parts: Religious Literature (Dharmasutra, Arthasastra, Monu, Smritisashtra, and Upanishad) and Buddhist Literature (Religious books of Buddha, Jataka, and Milind Pañhā). Anthropological components depend on inscriptions, though there are remarkable limitations (Ghosh, 2001).

The education system of that period was “Gurukul or Ashram” centric, and the mode of education was oral, though the Brahmi and Khorosthi alphabets were in use at this stage. This oral mode of education is called “Shruti”. Koutilya categorised this type of education into seven categories – i. Shusrusha (interest in hearing words from the Guru);

ii. Shraban (hearing the words with the ears);

iii. Grahan (realisation of the words);

iv. Dharan (Protect the words);

v. UahaPoho (discuss the words);

- vi. Binjyan (taking the complete knowledge about the meaning of the words);
- vii. Tattavinibesh (realisation of the internal meaning of the words) (Chatterjee, 1999; Pathak, 2008; Sarkar, 1979).

Education System in the Modern Period: There was no organised system of education from the Primary stage to the University level in this period. Ruling and wealthy Muslim families, recognising the value of education, made special arrangements for tutors for their children, along with the children of neighbours. Elementary schools called **Maktabas** are located in private houses or mosques, and for advanced education, students attend **Madrasahs**. But the Hindu system of education was the close and constant association of the teachers and taught, and the compulsory residence and training of the pupils in the teachers' house. The training period was a period of service, discipline and self-restraint. The Brahmins were the chief custodians and conservators of the Hindu learning. The mode of education was written and oral (Kapur, 2018).

Education System in the British Period: The education had been started in this period for the sake of oneself, i.e., to make English language knowing clerk though medium of instruction for education was not clearly decided whether it would be English or other Indian languages like, Hindi, Urdu, Sanskrit, Arabic, Persian, Gujarati, Marathi, Bengali, Tamil, Telugu, Kannada and many others. Establishment of regular educational institutions, such as Universities (Calcutta, Bombay, and Madras), Colleges, High Schools, Middle Schools, and Primary Schools, was undertaken. The mode of education was formal (Anjali, 2025).

Education System in the Post-Independence Period: The Constitution of India came into action on 26.01.1950. Several significant provisions that relate directly or indirectly to education have been included in the Constitution. The 86th Constitutional Amendment has made elementary education a fundamental right of children. Formal and informal educational institutions were set up. The mode of education was chalk-and-talk (Bhuker & Rose, 2023).

Education System with the application of Information and Communication Technology: The advent of ICT in education made a remarkable change in the education system in the following ways:

E – Learning System: The intended use of network-enabled Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching and learning is called the e-Learning system of education. The "e" refers here to electronic. It is a combination of a Learning Management System (LMS) and a Course Management System (CMS). Content is delivered here via Internet, Intranet or Extranet, Audio and

Video Tape, TV, CD-ROM, DVD and satellite. It may be text-driven, interactive, or simulation-based (E-learning System, n.d.).

Digital Learning Environment (DLE):The online environment of LMS, which includes tools and services purposefully brought together to support the needs of teaching and learning in all modes, to make a platform for managing course documents, quizzes, videos and the like (Lodge, Kennedy & Lockyer, 2020).

Virtual Learning Environment (VLE):It is a web-based platform for the digital aspects of the educational institutions' course of study. It presents resources, activities and interactions within a course structure and provides for the different stages of assessment (wiki). It supports a range of online interactions between learners and tutors (JISC, 2000 ; Virtual Learning Environment, n.d.).

Managed Learning Environment (MLE):"Learning management that synthesise the functionality of computer mediated communication and online method of delivering course materials" (Britain & Liber, 1999). It is the range of information systems and processes that contribute to an educational establishment's provision of learning and learning management (JISC, 2000 ; Boys,2002 ; Porter, n.d.)

MOOCs:

A Massive Open Online Course (MOOC), first coined by Dave Cormier in 2008, is an online course designed for large-scale, interactive participation and open access via the web. In addition to traditional course materials such as videos, readings, and problems etc, MOOCs provide interactive users for that help build community among students, professors, and teaching assistants. MOOCs are recent development in distance education.

“A MOOC is an online course that requires no prior qualifications for entry, can be accessed by anyone who has an Internet connection, and includes large or very large numbers of learners”– Commonwealth of learning, 2015 (Liyaganawardena, 2015 ; MIT World Peace University, 2023)

Blended Learning: It is also called the hybrid or mixed-mode of learning. It is the blending of traditional classroom teaching together with online education for the same students studying the same content in the same course. Live video, recorded video lectures and other digitally enabled learning opportunities can be a student's primary instructional interactions with other students and the teachers (Blending Learning, 202).

Learnings before and after the application of ICT:

Particulars	Learning in the Ancient Period	Learning in the Present Period
Students	Minimal	Increases as the population increases and as society develops
Teacher	Minimal	Trending to minimise the number of teachers
Approach to learning	Teacher-centered	Student/learner-centred
Access to information	Textbook and other reading materials in printed form	Textbook and other reading materials are available in printed forms as well as electronic forms too
Method of learning	Lecture method without visualisation	Lecture method with visualisation
Classroom	Classroom-based and time-bound	Anywhere, anytime beyond the classroom
Library	Physica Libraries	Digital and Virtual Libraries along with Physical Libraries

Findings:

- i. Education began in the Vedic period, not with the appearance of human beings on this Globe, and its description is based entirely on literary and anthropological components.
- ii. Two types of education were found in the modern period: a Hindu education system in which chiefly Brahmins are the conservators and custodians, and a residential education. On the other hand, Maktabas and Madrasahs were established by wealthy and ruling Muslim families for their own children, as well as for the children of neighbours.
- iii. During the British period, education was only for becoming an English-speaking clerk, though Calcutta University, Bombay University, and Madras University were established.
- iv. In the post-independence period, education is regarded as a Fundamental Right with the amendment of the Indian Constitution, which came into action on 26.01.1950.

- v. The drastic changes came into force with the advent of ICT in the learning system. E-Learning System, Digital Learning System, Virtual Learning Environment, Managed Learning Environment, MOOC and Blended Learning were introduced in learning.

Conclusion: The time has moved from the Industrial Age to the Information Age to the Knowledge Age. Success and survival depend on the efficient management of knowledge today. The efficient acquisition, storage, transfer, retrieval, application, and visualisation of knowledge differentiates successful from unsuccessful organisations.

In earlier eras, learning was teacher-controlled, resource-limited, and restricted. The present era is ICT-dominated, but it has not replaced the role of teachers or Gurus as it was in the ancient period. The role of the teachers has changed today. Now the teachers have been changed to mentors, facilitators and designers too. Above all, it can be said that "the basic pattern is almost the same".

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